
Public Policy on Food Security in Nigeria: An Evaluation of Goodluck Jonathan's Administration (2011-2015)

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Abstract: *The aim of this paper is to assess the public policy on food security adopted in Nigeria under President Goodluck Jonathan's administration from 2011 to 2015. It critically examines the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) targeted to uplift the level of Agricultural development in Nigeria. The theoretical framework adopted in this paper was the Systems theory (input-output model). Having utilized the secondary method of data collection, the paper therefore concluded that Agricultural Transformation Agenda impacted positively in the lives of farmers and significantly improved food production thereby boosting food security from 2011 to 2015. The paper lastly made some recommendations geared towards the current administration and subsequent ones borrowing a leaf from this to foster food security in our nation. .*

Key Words: Food Security, Public Policy, Agricultural Transformation Agenda

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Food is an important resource to human development and survival. As such, food is expected to be available for human existence. Nigeria's population is growing rapidly and this has made food supply to be insufficient to feed the populace, which in the long run indicates food insecurity. Food insecurity exists when the majority of

the people in a nation do not have access to food that is adequate in quality and quantity (Idachaba, 2004). Food security remains the central focus of Nigeria's agricultural sector since 1999. Nigeria has experienced some level of food insecurity as a result of mindless importation of food stuffs thus, the ability of the citizens to gain access to food deteriorated significantly and the food security position worsened because Nigerians were compelled to access food with high economic value.

Food security is very important to the development of a nation. Food security occurs where the quantity/quality of food is sufficient and available to the citizens of a country. Food or lack of it, has a strong effect on human destiny and subsequently on the nation. A nation is secure when the majority of the population has access to food of adequate quality and quantity, consistent at all times (Nwabah, 2005), and this brings to mind the issues of human security (food insecurity inclusive) which is best safeguarded through proactive and preventive action plans such as initiating an integrated policy that addresses food insecurity. Food is different from other commodities because everybody needs it for survival and it is an indispensable factor in the nation's quest for economic growth and political development.

A report by the Edo State Agricultural Development Program (2002) highlighted the prevailing situation. It reported that less than 5% of Nigerians are food secured, 65% are semi-food secured. Over 30% of Nigerians are facing the problem of food insecurity. Also Nigeria currently ranks as one of the major importers of food in the world (Abu, 2012). Even the various programmes and projects initiated by various governments in the past and present to rapidly improve the sector, reduce poverty and foreign exchange drain through food importation such as Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) Green Revolution (GR), National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), National Food Security Program, among others fell short of addressing food insecurity. (Ojo & Adebayo, 2012). Consequently, local farmers who had taken loan for the purpose of food production are now seriously indebted because of the acute competition of food imports. This is indeed a threat to National security, sustainable economic development and the hope of giving Nigerians a new lease of life.

Meanwhile, the underdeveloped status of the Nigerian economy is deeply rooted in the dependent structure of the economy which continues to deepen and aggravate the fundamental problems of economic transformation having an immediate bearing of food security. Hence, the level of agricultural development is interpreted in the context of the ruthless integration of the Nigerian economy into the world economy during the era of colonial expansion and currently under the strong wave of globalization which has shaped Nigerian economy. Nigeria's Fourth Republic has witnessed a high and rising cost of agricultural investments culminating into a high and rising cost of agricultural labour, the high cost of farm technology, inability of farmers to benefit fully from the sale of their agricultural commodity and the fact that development in other sectors of our economy has discouraged investment in agriculture.

The considerable expansion in petroleum production and export which according to Madujibeya (1976) diverted government attention from agriculture, especially after 1966 military came, as documented by Keith (1978) and Olayide (1975) confirmed that what has come to be known as the "food problem" has remained among the most dangerous threat to security and stability. Ake (1981), corroborates this by stating that the oil boom itself diverted attention away from other sectors of the economy, particularly agriculture. He states further that Nigeria has progressively grown incapable of feeding herself and depends on food imports from the West.

Robinson (1995), noted that with the rural to urban shift and few people to work on farm led to insufficient food production. This food shortage leads to higher prices. In Nigeria, many food items like rice are being imported instead of boosting rice production locally. Embarking on importation of food instead of producing them will be a drag on the nation's economy (Olaloku, Fajana, Tommon, and Ukpong, 1997). Uko-Aviomah (2005) gave some reasons why food insecurity must be avoided. These are based on the effects of food insecurity which are as follows;

- (i) Malnutrition: Deterioration in health of the citizens, occurrence of high blood pressure, and nutritional deficiency diseases

- (iii) Increase in social vices such as begging, ritual sacrifices, prostitution, armed robbery, child labour, juvenile delinquency, hunger, unemployment etc;
- (iv) Production of mean citizens that lack self-esteem and low integrity;
- (v) High infant mortality rate; and
- (vi) Low life span
- (vii) Increase in divorce rate.

In addition Nwabah (2005) explained that lack of food has strong effects on human destiny and also on the nation. Bald (1999) stated that lack of food security will slow down a nation's development and will also seriously disrupt farm input, provision of infrastructural facilities and employing new techniques. The mono-cultural oil export-led economy of the country has adversely affected agricultural (food) production in the country. It is important to note that, if Nigeria is to meet her vision 2020, agricultural sector must, as a matter of priority, be revived by government through sound policies that will encourage the sector and boost food production. The most important national priority therefore is to feed the population, because the continuous existence of human beings depends solely on adequate provision of food. Although, in accomplishing this onerous task, successive Nigerian governments since independence in 1999 have formulated various agricultural policies and programs. Nonetheless, the failures of these programmes out-weighed the successes; hence there is no adequate food security for the teeming Nigerian population. Obviously, considering the huge relationship between food security and political stability in the country, this study becomes desirable.

Therefore, this study will evaluate the public policy on food security directly in Nigeria under the Goodluck Jonathan administration with the intention of successive governments borrowing a leaf from it and tapping into its achievements.

II. Conceptual Clarification

Food Security: Food security is a condition related to the supply of food and individuals' ability to gaining access to it. Concerns over food security have existed throughout history. At the 1974 World Food Conference, the term "food security" was defined with an emphasis on supply. Food security, they said, is the "availability at all times of adequate world food supplies of basic foodstuffs to sustain a steady expansion of food consumption and to offset fluctuations in production and prices". (United Nations,2013). Later definitions added demand and access issues to the definition. The final report of the 1996 World Food Summit stated that food security "exists when all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life". (United Nations, 2015). Household food security exists when all members, at all times, have access to enough food for an active, healthy life. (USDA, 2008) Individuals who are food secure do not live in hunger or fear of starvation. [FAO, 2006). Food insecurity, on the other hand, is a situation of "limited or uncertain availability of nutritionally adequate and safe foods or limited or uncertain ability to acquire acceptable foods in socially acceptable ways", according to the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) (2008). Food security incorporates a measure of resilience to future disruption or unavailability of critical food supply due to various risk factors including droughts, shipping disruptions, fuel shortages, economic instability, and wars. (Boeing, 2016). In the years 2011-2017, an estimated 842 million people were suffering from chronic hunger (FAO, 2017). The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, or FAO, identified the four pillars of food security as availability, access, utilization and stability(FAO, 2009). The United Nations (UN) recognized the Right to Food in the Declaration of Human Rights in 1948 (United Nations, 2015) and has since noted that it is vital for the enjoyment of all other rights. (United Nations, 2015).

Nigerian Economy and Food Security

Successive government in Nigeria has since independence in 1960, pursued the goal of structural changes with much success. The growth dynamics have been propelled by the existence and exploitation of natural resources and primary products, since 1999, the country returned to the path of civil democratic governance and has sustained uninterrupted democratic rule for a period of 16 years. The successive civilian administration since 1999 have committed to tackling the daunting challenges. Sanusi (2010) posit that the economic growth has risen substantially, with annual average of 7.4 percent in the last decade; but the growth has not been inclusive, broad-based and transformational. Agriculture (food) and services have been the main drivers of growth. Obamiro (2005) argue that the implication of this trend is that economic growth in Nigeria has not resulted in the desired structural changes that would make manufacturing the engine of growth, create employment, promote technological development and induce poverty alleviation. Abuh (2012) observes that in the light of power performance of the economy since independence despite the huge mineral, material and human endowment, as well as the accelerating dynamics of the global and economy. The prospects of the economy in the short-to-medium term moves from the historical sluggish growth trends to a vibrant growth pith that can transform the structure of the economy and enable her attainment of the vision enunciated under vision 20:20:20 and launch her into the league of advanced economy.

Structurally, the Nigerian economy can be classified into three major sectors namely primary agriculture and natural resources; secondary-processing and manufacturing and tertiary services sectors. The agricultural sector is in and mixture of subsistence and modern farming, while the industrial section comprises modern business enterprises which co-exist with a large number of micro-enterprises employing less than 10 persons mainly located in the informal sector. (Sanusi 2010; Dauda 2006; Adebayo 2010). The agricultural sector has not able to fulfil its additional role of feeding the population, meeting the raw material needs of industries and providing surplus for export. Sanusi (2010), opines that Nigerian economy has not experience remarkable transformation and restructuring indicating that Nigeria has become a trading outpost for goods produced elsewhere with little democratic transformation of the output of primary sectors by the secondary sector. This is so since the Nigerian agriculture is really peasant and high contribution of tertiary sectors to output suggest that the sector is not really servicing the Nigerian economy but, indeed the economies of her trading partners.

Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA)

Agricultural policy is a statement of action and a fundamental tool employed by any nation in achieving agricultural development (FAO 2004) while Agricultural policy change refers to incremental shifts in existing structures, or new and innovative policies (Bennett and Howlett, 1992). It is a generalized statement that Nigeria's agriculture has suffered some neglect due to reliance on oil and gas resources and inappropriate policies and institution. Also, in the recent time, there have been a lot of concerns expressed over the looming danger of food crisis in many nations, including Nigeria. Nigeria agricultural policies have undergone changes especially in the 4th republic. These changes have been a mere reflection of changes in government or administration (Amalu, 1998). This is because these policies vary only in nomenclature and organizational network

The Agricultural Transformation Agenda of the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development was directly built on the Goodluck Jonathan's transformation agenda thrust. Agriculture is an important sector of the Nigerian economy with a high potential for employment creation, food security and poverty reduction (Eme, Okechukwu I, & Onyishi, Anthony O. 2014). However, these potentials have remained largely untapped which has led to the dwindling performance of the agricultural sector both domestically and in the international trade over the years. It was against this background that the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) aggressively attempted to implement an Agricultural Transformation Agenda. (Vanguard, 2015).

The vision of the transformation strategy is to achieve a hunger-free Nigeria through an agricultural sector that drives income growth, accelerate achievement of food and nutritional security, generate employment and transform Nigeria into a leading player in global food markets and to grow wealth for millions of farmers. Thus the focus was to assure food security, reduce expenditure on foreign exchange on food imports, diversify the economy, generate foreign exchange and create jobs. In order to achieve this vision, a dynamic approach was introduced regarding agriculture as a business, not as a development programme. Fertilizer procurement and distribution, marketing institutions, financial value chains and agricultural investment framework were to be restructured.

According to a report by African Development Fund's (ADF-ATASP-1) 2013, the fertilizer strategy enhanced and stimulate the growth of the private sector fertilizer industry sequel to inefficiency in the government distribution system and wastage of resources. It is thus believed that the subsistence farmers would be moved from their high poverty level through market oriented/market surplus facilitated by Nigerian Incentive Based Risk Sharing for Agricultural Lending (NIRSAL) into a commercialized system that would facilitate trade and competitiveness. This according to the action plan, was achieved through the Growth Enhancement Support (GES) an Investment that is targeted at 20 million farmers at an estimated cost per year of 5,000 naira. In addition the agenda included, the improvement in rural infrastructure, establishment of staple crop processing zone to attract the private sector into areas of production in order to reduce post-harvest losses, add value to locally produced crops and foster rural economic growth.(Abbott,2009).

The impact of the Agriculture Transformation Agenda (ATA)

In 2014, according to experts Agricultural Transformation Agenda has contributed in making agriculture a viable sector of the Nigerian economy. Hence, there are anticipations among many Nigerians that agriculture in the face of plummeting oil prices, serve as a buffer for the Nigerian economy. According to Ruth T.N 2014 in this analysis concludes that 2015 was a defining year for Nigeria's agriculture. The federal government with great optimism had asserted that

"With the ATA on course, the fall in the price of oil or devaluation of the naira will not lead to the collapse of the Nigerian economy in 2015 but rather the stringent commitments and investments in the sector will yield high dividends that create buffer for the economy in 2015"

The Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA), launched in 2012, was an initiative of the Federal Ministry of Agricultural and Rural Development to support the President Goodluck Jonathans Transformation Agenda. The goal of the ATA is to *build commodity value chains* and the institutions required to unlock the country's huge agricultural potentials with the targeted outcome such as add 20 million tonnes of food to the domestic food supply by the year 2015, create 3.4 million jobs and ensuring import substitution through the acceleration of production of local staples aimed at reducing dependence on food imports and turning Nigeria into a net food exporter. A major success story of the ATA in 2014, was the news that Nigerian Food import bill had dropped by N466bn thereby adding N780bn to the economy during the period. While Many Nigerians have applauded the development in the nation's agricultural sector, many are also of the view that the claims to a drop in the nations' food import bill does not correspond with markets development as the prices of food and agricultural commodities have remained on the rise despite claims to huge gains in the sector. According to the then Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development, Dr Akinwumi Adeshina, he said,

"We aimed at diversifying the economy and we have, because of the food production and the fact that we have produced over 21 million metric tonnes of additional food that has created the buffer that we see today."

Development on Agricultural Transformation Agenda and Public Policy on Food Security in 2011 - 2015

Pointers in 2014 had indicated that the agricultural sector was experiencing its greatest boom since the discovery of oil in the late 60s with the setting up of ATA aimed at making agriculture more attractive to not just the ageing farmers but to Youths through the Growth Enhancement Support Scheme (GES).

The GES was designed to capture agricultural development following a value chain approach of various commodities to capture all interest groups including men, women and the youths with the launch of Nagropreneus by the President in 2012.

According to Akpan (2017), records sourced with the Ministry showed that over 14 million farmers were registered in the ATA data base to benefit from the Growth Enhancement Scheme (GES), with over 10 million of those farmers being northern beneficiaries. ATA developed Nigeria's first ever database of farmers, so we can identify farmers and manage farmer's identity "Over 14.5 million farmers was registered in the past three years". Despite the optimism of government, stakeholders have expressed doubt at the level of success, insisting that the figures of success are not tallying with reality."

In the work of abuh (2012) it shows that records from the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development revealed that Private sector investments in fertilizer manufacturing expanded, with over \$5 billion private sector investments in fertilizer manufacturing from 2011 to 2015. It further revealed that the sector witnessed a turn around as the share of total bank lending expanded from about 2% in 2011 to 5% by 2013. Bank lending to seed companies and agro-input dealers expanded from \$10 million in 2012 to \$53 million in 2013; while bank lending to fertilizer companies expanded from \$100 million in 2012 to \$500 million by 2014. Ukase (2007) also to be recalled that President Goodluck Jonathan also launched a N50 Billion farm mechanization policy drive to take hoes and cutlasses into the museums and replace them with affordable and appropriate modern farm machinery" in the view of Itodo (2016), the year 2015 marked an end of year policy document from the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. It assured that the sugar industry will experience an upsurge in fortune and that the quantum of national revenue that has been going into sugar importation is unsustainable, particularly in the context of dwindling oil fortunes and devaluation of naira. In 2015, Nigeria became a net exporter of rice, away from the decades of annual importation that has cost the country an average of N1 billion daily. Despite the new involvement of billionaires in rice farming, the small farmers will still continue to contribute significantly.

Policy Thrust and Objective of Agricultural Transformation Agenda under Goodluck Jonathan Administration

The Vision of the Agricultural Transformation Agenda is to achieve a food secured Nigeria through an agricultural sector that drives income growth, accelerates achievement of food and nutritional security, generates employment and transforms Nigeria into a leading player in global food market to grow wealth for millions of farmers. Thus the overall sector goal of the proposed agenda is to contribute to employment generation and shared wealth creation along the commodity value chain, as well as food and nutritional security. Its specific objective is to increase, on a sustainable basis, the income of smallholder farmers and rural entrepreneurs that are engaged in the production, processing, storage and marketing of the selected commodity value chains. Federal Ministry of Agricultural and Rural Development (FMARD 2012) reported that the following measures were to be taken towards attaining success:

1. There shall be an end to the era of treating agriculture as a development project
2. There shall be no more isolated projects without a strategic focus to drive agricultural growth and food security in a clear and measurable way.
3. There shall be an end to 'big government' crowding out the private sector.

4. The Agricultural Transformation Agenda was executed to support Mr. President's Transformation Agenda
5. Agriculture is focused on as a business and not a mere program.
6. The transformation of the agricultural sector utilized to create jobs, create wealth and ensure food security.
7. Value chains had a focused where Nigeria has comparative advantage.
8. Strategic partnerships was developed to stimulate investments to drive a market-led agricultural transformation through state and local governments, inter-ministerial collaboration, private sector and farmer groups and civil society.
9. There was a sharp focus on youth and women Transformation policies

The transformation policies involve a change in our approach to agricultural sector. Specifically, the following shall be restructured: fertilizer procurement and distribution, marketing institutions, financial value chains and agricultural investment framework.

Other Supportive Activities of Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA)

Value Chain Coordination- The agricultural transformation agenda was saddled with task of developing and implementing strategies to grow Nigerian agriculture along with targeted agricultural commodity value chain like Rice, Sorghum, Cassava, Maize, Cocoa, cotton etc

Investment Frameworks for Agriculture – Agricultural transformation agenda provided appropriate fiscal, investment and infrastructural policies for staple crop processing zones. Such policies included tax breaks on import of agricultural processing equipment, tax holiday for food processors that located in the zones and supportive infrastructure especially complimentary investment buy the government in roads, logistics, storage facilities and power.

Marketing Information System – The agricultural policies developed an efficient agricultural marketing system that was promoted through the provision of adequate market information. The buyer of last resort mechanism built into the marketing system and provided price stabilization effect on the system.

Stakeholders Perspective on the effectiveness of the policies, Regulations and Institutions on Nigeria's Agriculture

Opinions on the effectiveness of the policies and regulations in the different areas of agriculture were sought from both policy makers and policy implementers. In general, policies aimed at stimulating on-farm production (fertilizer strategy) rank highest. These include those policies aimed at stimulating agricultural production for domestic market, agricultural input demand by farmers, domestic agricultural commodity trade, agricultural input supply to farmers and domestic investment in agriculture. It is evident from the ranking that the more effective policies and regulations are those targeted to upstream agricultural production activities and geared towards the domestic market. Agricultural transformation agenda enhanced post-production activities such as commodity storage made available in the crop processing zones.

Meanwhile policies and regulations on food security and poverty reduction (which are indeed offshoot of domestic agricultural production), other policies and regulations associated with improved human welfare ranked very low. But overall policies on foreign investment ranked lowest. From the foregoing, it can be seen that agricultural transformation agenda are more effective in the primary production subsector of agriculture than in the downstream subsector. Impact of policies on the welfare status of the people and on the environment remains weak. In general the trust of the effective policies has bearing on boosting agricultural production for food self-sufficiency.

Roles of Public Sector in Agricultural Transformation Agenda

Agricultural sector has high potential for tackling socioeconomic challenges including high levels of income, poverty and food insecurity. Given the importance of the sector as a source of livelihood for the large majority of the population, and a base for foreign exchange earnings; the sector deserve adequate public and private sector investment for attaining and maintaining the anticipated high growth rate. This remains a critical challenge for agricultural transformation in Nigeria (Mlingi and Rajab, 2009). Public investment in the sector should be directed towards infrastructure development that include rehabilitation of existing rural and agricultural infrastructures and establishing new ones to help in mitigating impacts of climate change, restore soil fertility, remove barriers to domestic trade and flows of food. The focus of agricultural transformation will be to create a favorable policy and regulatory framework that will lead to enhanced quality compliance with local, regional and international standards; facilitate measures that will promote private sector investment into the sector and create room for strengthened public private partnership. To that effect, the following areas will be emphasized during implementation:

Enhance capacity in value addition and agro processing: The thrust will be placed to broaden institutional capacities to specifically provide services related to value addition and agro processing such as quality assurance, inspection and certification and take concrete steps to enhance knowledge and information sharing amongst the relevant stakeholders on agro processing and value addition. In addition, the public investment will be extended to provide support and improve the expansion of the degree of processing (secondary and tertiary industries), so as to increase the share of product prices and strengthen incentive structure

for private sector participation in agro-processing and value addition. The aim of this component is to encourage, promote and support public and private sectors to invest in agro processing and value addition activities to increase competitiveness of locally produced agricultural products to satisfy domestic and export markets. Subsequently, the sub sector will be enabled to play a driving role in the economic development of the country, add greater value to raw materials, and generate employment, wealth and foreign exchange. Although the agro-processing sub sector is currently underdeveloped, it has the potential to be a key driver of development. The country has significant untapped potential to add value to existing raw materials, agricultural and marine products. In terms of crops, food crop commodities such as cassava, sweet potatoes, banana, mangoes, oranges, pineapples and tomatoes can potentially be produced to the amounts sufficient for processing and value addition. Recent study on the post harvest losses of crops, livestock and fish (Mlingi and Rajab, 2009) estimated that post-harvest losses of fish in processing, preservation and notably in storage averages 10 percent while the overall loss in the whole value chain is estimated at 25 percent per year.

Human and institution capacity: The public investment will be directed towards enhancing institutional and human resource capacity, prompting efficiency through appropriate incentive and motivation packages to scientists and professional staff and to support and strengthen capacity of producer institutions for them to adequately participate in provision of support services necessary for implementing agricultural transformation agenda. Specifically, the initiative will focus on:

Institutional strengthening and human capacity: Support will be availed to strengthen the institutional capacity for managing agricultural development and increase the ability to cope up with emerging challenges by putting in place a system of coordination, and empowering the relevant institutions by providing them with adequate resources both financial and human. Public investment will also include developing scientific and professional human capacity so as to benefit from technological opportunities. Emphasis will be to create proper working environment for scientists to efficiently deliver and to put in place clear framework for implementing human resource development programme specifically addressing gaps in high-technology areas.

Support creation and strengthening of trade unions, producer organizations and farmers groups: Farmers and trade organizations should be prepared and empowered to demand and access support services provide by public and private sectors; to take part on the design, implementation and monitoring of agricultural projects and to

further participate in the process of commercializing the sector and to demand favourable national policies and legislations to effectively and efficiently guide the sector.

Commercializing agricultural production: The main focus of this component is to promote the development of value chains of a few selected high value commodities based on comparative advantage, farmer preference and market demand through: a) transformation of subsistence smallholder farming into viable commercial production units that are feasible for private sector investment (service provision, market access); b) promoting adequate utilization of productive land and industrial resources through joint venture schemes (medium to large scale firms) for increasing employment and agricultural output; c) enhanced investment in identified priorities areas to increase agricultural output.

Promoting youth involvement in agriculture: The current proportion of youth population engaged in agricultural activities is very low. This makes agricultural labour force being dominated by women and old aged population. Youth involvement/engagement to the sector

is constrained by low production and productivity embedded in the sector, high risks and uncertainty, low returns and declining terms of trade as compared to the other sectors of the economy (Amani, 2010). To facilitate agricultural transformation, it is critical that this trend is reversed. This trend therefore, necessitates for targeted interventions to promote youth participation in agriculture as well as provide specific incentives to the youth for entry into the agriculture sector. Under agricultural transformation agenda the focus will be on encouraging youth to realize their potential through investing in agriculture and count agriculture as a productive way of life whilst benefiting from employment opportunities. Special efforts will be undertaken to place youth confined in a range of viable agricultural enterprises where they will be exposed to operations, practical skills and processes, farm management skills (FMARD, 2001). Government will facilitate the process and continue to develop and maintain a favorable macro-economic policy environment conducive for private sector participation in the proposed agricultural transformation. These will focus specifically on the provision of support services required for increasing and sustaining agricultural production and productivity, growth of real farm incomes, and household food security.

III. Theoretical Framework

In explaining this study, the system theory (input and output analysis), and structural functionalism theory would be used. The input output version of the system theory would be adopted for this study, basically to explain the analysis of public policy on food security in Nigeria. David Easton defined political system theory as ‘that system of interaction in any society through which binding or authoritative allocation are made and implemented. According to Easton, it is the making of binding or authoritative allocations which distinguishes the political system from other system both within and outside the overall society that form the environment of a political system.

The political system received input from the society in form of demand and support. In other words, inputs can be defined briefly as constituted by the demands made upon the political system and the supports of the system itself. Demands input are those claims, demands and requests on the decision making authority (the political system). And these could be in form of demand for provision of storage facilities, provision of fertilizers, demand for addressing farm animal diseases, demand for reduced price of food items etc.

According to Easton, the inputs consist of demands and supports received by the system from the society. A demand is “an expression of opinion that an authoritative allocation with regards to a particular subject matter should or should not be made by those responsible for doing so According to the report by FOA ADP (2002), less than 5% of Nigerians are food secured and over 30% are facing food insecurity.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the study conclude that the vision of the Agricultural Transformation Agenda stimulate growth in the sector due to the fact that the change of orientation of agricultural policies from

development program to that of business-like attitude driven by the private sector. In conclusion, the Agricultural Transformation Agenda impacted positively in the lives of farmers and significantly improved food production thereby boosting food security from 2011 to 2015.

Recommendations

In view of the remarkable achievement of the Agricultural Transformation Agenda embarked upon by the Jonathan Administration as well as the deplorable state that the Agricultural sector has delved into after his administration, this paper recommends that:

The current administration and subsequent ones should borrow a leaf from the Jonathan Administration by embarking on Agriculture as a serious business and not a mere program.

Secondly, the current administration and subsequent ones must endeavour to genuinely tackle insecurity especially banditry and the farmers-herders clashes which has immensely put fear in the farmers thus, preventing them from going to their farms which has drastically reduced food production culminating in the recent rise in food cost.

Thirdly, loans should be made more available to the farmers by current administration and subsequent ones as well as the provision of fertilizers and mechanised farming to boost food production.

Finally as agriculture has transcended from development strategy to agric business, the private sector should partner with government and non-government organizations to make the best of the situation. Government should intensify efforts in the Public Private Partnership (PPP) between local and foreign companies. This partnership could import some necessary technology that could be used to harness some benefits from agriculture especially with Israel that has made a breakthrough in agriculture. Thus dynamic public policy is the way forward in transforming the agricultural sector in Nigeria.

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